

COMPARISON OF FOUR PROGRAMMING LANGUAGES USED FOR COMMUNICATION WITH MEASURING INSTRUMENTS

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***Rezime:** Today, computers are applied in measurements across all economic and industrial sectors. The application of computers in metrology has led to significant changes in measurement techniques, particularly concerning electrical quantities. Various programming languages are used for communication and control of measuring instruments, each with its own strengths and weaknesses. This paper provides a comparative analysis of the properties and characteristics of several popular programming languages: Visual Basic, C++, and Python, as well as VEEPro, a language specifically designed for communication with programmable measuring instruments. The similarities and differences between these four programming languages are primarily aimed at educators teaching programming and electrical measurements in schools and universities. For this study, we developed programs to compare the execution speed of these languages across a large number of cycles. All the obtained results are presented in tabular form in this paper.*

***Ključne reči:** Programming Language, Comparison, Execution Speed.*

1. Introduction

The final activity in the process of overhauling turbojet engines, before their installation on an aircraft, involves testing on a stationary testing station. These stands are specialized facilities designed to simulate all operating regimes an engine may encounter during flight. A large number of engine parameters are measured on the testing station. These parameters are captured over a short period, encompassing the engine, the mounting

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platform, and the test cell where the engine is housed. Compared to the number of signals measured during an actual flight, significantly more signals are captured on the test stand, covering both the engine and its mounting platform. These measurement systems are characterized by a complex structure and high measurement performance, meeting stringent criteria mandated for the testing of aeronautical equipment and engines intended for modern aircraft. All recordings on the testing station aim to detect and eliminate any potential issues with the engine on the ground before its installation in an aircraft. Once installed, the engine must achieve exceptional reliability across all operating regimes encountered during flight [1]. Implementing a measurement-acquisition system on a stationary testing station for turbojet engine testing is one of the most complex engineering tasks in the field of measurement and programming.

The advantages of implementing such a system include:

1. High-speed measurement of a large number of diverse signals,
2. Reduced measurement uncertainty,
3. Flexibility in processing, expressing, and presenting measurement results,
4. Real-time acquisition of corrected engine parameters.

During the development of various measurement-acquisition systems, multiple programming languages were utilized. The choice of programming language for communication and control of measurement instruments often posed a challenge. Programming languages are an inexhaustible topic of discussion in the professional community today, debating which language is better and why a programmer or company chose to develop software using it. In recent decades, numerous programming languages have emerged to address practical problems more efficiently. Some languages have simpler syntax, making them easier to learn and more suitable for education, while others, with more complex syntax, are better suited for solving intricate problems in specialized fields. Every language has its advantages and limitations. This paper provides a comparative analysis of the features and characteristics of some popular programming languages: Visual Basic, C++, and Python, as well as VEEPro, which is specifically designed for communication with programmable measurement instruments. VEEPro is primarily intended for interfacing computers with Hewlett Packard, Agilent, and today's Keysight instruments. However, it is also successfully used for interfacing with other well-known brands of programmable instruments.

This variety of programming languages serves to demonstrate the fundamental differences in syntax to educators teaching programming and electrical measurements at schools and universities [2]. It highlights which languages are simpler for beginners. For this study, programs were developed to compare execution speeds for various tasks over multiple cycles. These tasks include addition and division, calculating sine values and natural logarithms, sorting arrays, and writing/reading data to/from text files and Excel documents. Each program underwent 10 measurements of execution time, with the standard deviation of time dispersion and the relative deviation of the standard deviation from the mean calculated. All results are presented in tabular format.

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2. Literature review

The integration of computers and programming languages into the field of measurement has revolutionized the way measurements are conducted, enabling efficient management of multiple measurement instruments or systems that collect data from a vast number of sensors. Several studies have compared the performance and syntax of various programming languages used for communicating with these measurement systems. This paper provides a brief overview of some key works that discuss the comparative analysis of different programming languages.

Naim et al. (2010) conducted a comprehensive survey that compared ten programming languages, including C++, C#, Java, JavaScript, Haskell, PHP, Scala, Scheme, and BPEL, based on criteria like secure programming practices, web application development, web service composition, and various programming paradigms such as object-oriented, functional, and declarative programming [3]. This study highlights the strengths and limitations of each language, showing how they address different needs and tasks.

In a study by Stein & Geyer-Schulz (2013), C++, C#, Java, F#, and Python were analyzed in a controlled experiment where each language was tasked with solving a graph clustering problem [4]. Their findings indicated that C++ provided the best performance in terms of execution time, while Java, C#, and F# exhibited similar performance under certain conditions. Additionally, the study pointed out that modern languages like Python and F# offer advantages in reducing the size of the overall codebase.

Zakaria et al. (2015) focused on a comparative study of six programming languages: C++, C#, PHP, Java, Python, and Visual Basic evaluating them based on reusability, portability, reliability, efficiency, and other attributes [5]. The study offers a comprehensive look at the strengths and weaknesses of these languages, providing valuable insights for developers looking to choose the most appropriate language for specific tasks.

Parveen & Fatima (2016) explored Java, C#, and C++ in their comparison, considering factors like syntax, execution speed, flexibility, and compilation time [6]. By running a common program across all three languages, the researchers were able to assess the performance and usability of each language in a standardized manner, helping developers to make informed decisions based on the performance characteristics of the languages.

Pejovic (2019) highlighted the use of Python for automating measurement systems and creating virtual measurement instruments [7]. The study emphasized Python's flexibility and its extensive range of modules that support communication with measurement devices, making it an ideal tool for modernizing measurement techniques in various fields, including power electronics and metrology.

Pereira et al. (2021) examined the efficiency of programming languages from an energy consumption perspective [8]. Their study utilized 27 programming languages and tested them against ten standardized challenges, providing valuable insights into energy-efficient programming practices and helping developers optimize their code with energy efficiency in mind.

Ali & Qayyum (2021) compared the performance of C, C++, Python, and Java based on execution time, speed, and simplicity [9]. They used an optimized pseudo-code example to demonstrate how these languages perform when executing the same task, offering a practical comparison of their efficiency and ease of use.

Chiu et al. (2022) analyzed Java, JavaScript, Go, and Python, benchmarking them against C++ as a reference [10]. They focused on runtime performance, resource utilization, and scalability, providing a detailed comparison of how these languages handle dynamic type checking and memory usage.

Languages developed in the 1950s, such as Fortran, remain in active use today, owing to their versatility and foundational role in supporting a substantial portion of the legacy systems and applications in our digital landscape. Since that era, numerous additional languages have emerged, exhibiting increasing diversity over time. Modern languages such as C, C++, Python, Java, JavaScript, and PHP have greatly enhanced efficiency and are utilized across a wide array of applications. Sakharkar (2023) noted that while modern languages such as C++, Java, Python, and JavaScript have enhanced efficiency, they also introduce new security challenges, requiring a careful approach to safeguard against vulnerabilities [11].

Zakeri-Nasrabadia et al. (2023) performed a meta-analysis of code similarity measurement techniques, offering insights into tools used to evaluate and compare code across various programming languages [12]. Their research emphasizes the importance of understanding code similarity when assessing programming languages and applications. Notably, nearly 49% of these tools are tailored for Java programs, while 37% are compatible with C and C++.

Srinivasappa et al. (2023) proposed a smart routing method for real-time data applications in Mobile Ad hoc Networks (MANETs), comparing several routing protocols [13]. Their work demonstrates how the principles of programming and routing can be integrated into IoT systems to improve the efficiency and reliability of real-time applications. In conclusion, the traffic-aware EQMRP protocol offers a significant improvement in QoS for real-time IoT applications in MANETs.

Ramanathan et al. (2023) introduced a novel approach for reducing interference in MIMO systems using time-shifted pilot contamination strategies [14]. Their research contributes to the development of communication systems that rely heavily on programming languages for optimization and performance. Comparative experimental analysis, conducted using the MATLAB tool, pitted this method against two conventional techniques: Integer Linear Programming (ILP) and Q-Learning based Interference Control (QLIC).

Jäger & Gümmer (2023) explored PythonDAQ, an open-source Python package designed for measurement data acquisition and post-processing [15]. This tool showcases Python's potential in the domain of measurement systems, offering an alternative to commercial data acquisition solutions.

In their 2023 study, Alves et al. compared the linguistic features of six prominent programming languages (C, C++, C#, Java, Python, and Haskell), identifying key differences that affect programmer familiarity and performance [16]. This study provides insights into how language choice can impact programming efficiency. This suggests that

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inquiries related to Java, C, and Python may yield more significant insights into their defining characteristics. In contrast, familiarity with Haskell, C++, and C# was notably lower, with only 47%, 45%, and 31% of respondents, respectively, claiming they were at least somewhat proficient in these languages.

Katzy et al. (2023) reported that certain languages, such as C++, Python, and Java, exhibit similar token representations, while others, like Mathematica and R, differ significantly [17]. Their findings suggest that language similarity could impact performance in multi-language applications, underscoring the importance of language selection in system design.

Padilla et al. (2023) investigated the use of ChatGPT in programming education, exploring its benefits and challenges in coding tasks [18]. The study highlights how AI tools like ChatGPT can enhance coding efficiency but also raises concerns about ethical implications and data privacy. The findings highlight several benefits, such as improved coding efficiency, assistance in comprehending complex code, and its role as a problem-solving tool. Conversely, the research underscores significant challenges, including concerns about data privacy, ethical implications, tendencies toward plagiarism, and limitations in contextual comprehension.

3. Comparison of basic command syntax across programming languages

In this section of the paper, we aim to compare the syntax of some basic commands in the four programming languages under consideration.

In Visual Basic and C++, it is mandatory to declare each variable before using it in the program code. On the other hand, in Python and VEEPro, it is not necessary to predeclare variables before they are used in the code. Table 1 presents an example of declaring variables X1 and Y1 as integers, followed by assigning the value of X1 incremented by 1 to the variable Y1.

For the C++ programming language, it is characteristic that each variable declaration or value assignment must end with a semicolon (;). Omitting this symbol while writing the code is one of the most common errors when programming in C++.

Every programming language includes branching structures. Table 1 provides an example of an IF THEN ELSE branching structure, demonstrated through the calculation of the modulus of the number X. We believe that the simplest way to write this structure is in Visual Basic, as it is easy to follow the beginning and end of the branching structure, especially when there are nested branches. In Visual Basic, it is recommended but not mandatory to ensure that commands belonging to the same block are indented consistently from the start of the line. This significantly reduces errors in program code compared to other observed programming languages.

Python also has a simple and concise structure; however, one drawback is that a colon (:) must follow the branching condition and the "else" command. Additionally, care must be taken to ensure all commands within the same block are indented consistently from the start of the line.

In C++, each programming structure begins and ends with curly braces ({ and }). It is also essential to ensure that all commands in the same block are indented consistently from the start of the line.

Figure 1 shows the **IF THEN ELSE** branching structure in the VEEPro programming language, implemented using predefined objects that are connected by lines. The lines determine the execution order of individual blocks in the VEEPro programming language.

Table 1. IF THEN ELSE Branching Structure Visual Basic, C++ and Python

Visual Basic	C++	Python
<pre>Dim X, Y As Integer X=Text1.Text If X<0 Then Y= -X Else Y=X EndIf</pre>	<pre>int main() { int X, Y; printf ("Input X: "); scanf ("%d", &X); if (X<0) { Y= -X; } else { Y=X; } }</pre>	<pre>X = int(input("Input value X: ")) if X < 0: Y = -X else: Y = X</pre>

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Figure 1. IF THEN ELSE Branching Structure in VEEPro

Note: This figure was prepared by the authors

Every programming language has iterative structures. Table 2 presents an example of a two FOR loop structure with a finite number 100 000 000 of iterations for summing values. We believe that the simplest way to write this structure is in Visual Basic, as it is easy to track the beginning and end of the repetition structure. In Python, the code is the shortest. In Python, one must simply ensure that when specifying the desired number of iterations, the upper limit of the loop should be increased by 1 compared to the code in other programming languages.

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Table 2. FOR loop structure Visual Basic, C++ and Python

Visual Basic	C++	Python
<pre>Dim i, j, sum As Integer sum = 0 For i = 1 To 10000 For j = 1 To 10000 sum = i+j Next j Next i</pre>	<pre>int main() { int i, j, sum; sum = 0; for (int i=1; i<=10000; i++) { for (int j=1; j<=10000; j++) { sum = i+j; } } }</pre>	<pre>sum = 0 for i in range(1, 10001): for j in range(1, 10001): sum = i + j</pre>

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

In Table 3, an example of a WHILE loop structure is provided, which repeats 1000 times, and within it, the sum of even numbers is calculated. We believe that the simplest way to write this structure is in Visual Basic, as it is very easy to track the beginning and end of the repeating structure. In Python, one must pay attention to the fact that after commands like „if“, „else“, „for“ and „while“, a colon (:) is required. Additionally, care should be taken to ensure that all commands within a block are consistently indented from the start of the line.

Table 3. WHILE loop structure Visual Basic, C++ and Python

Visual Basic	C++	Python
<pre>Dim J, X As Integer J = 0 X=0 Do While J < 1000 If J MOD 2= 0 Then X=X+J End If J = J + 1 Loop</pre>	<pre>int main() { int J = 0; int X = 0; while (J < 1000) { if (J % 2 == 0) { X = X + J; } J = J + 1; } }</pre>	<pre>J = 0 X = 0 while J < 1000: if J % 2 == 0: X = X + J J = J + 1</pre>

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

4. Results of comparing execution speeds of programming languages

In this section of the paper, we aim to present the results of comparing the execution speed of the same program code in four programming languages, which we have compared with each other. Each program was executed ten times on the same computer running the Windows operating system. Based on the ten execution time measurements, the average value and the standard deviation for the ten measurements were calculated.

This discrepancy suggests that while we can observe variations in performance, the exact reasons behind these differences are not easily pinpointed. Several factors, such as the underlying optimizations of each language, compiler behavior, operating system-level processes, and even hardware-related variables, could be affecting the execution times.

Despite the use of the same hardware and operating system, the results highlight the complexities of performance evaluation across different programming environments.

In Table 4, we present the comparative results of measuring the time taken to sum two numbers within a double For loop. Each loop is executed 10,000 times, resulting in a total of 100,000,000 cycles for Visual Basic, C++, and Python. For VEEPro, measurements were taken with only 10,000 cycles, as it was observed that the For loop in this language runs much slower compared to the other three languages.

Based on the data shown in Tables 4, 5, 6, and 7, we can observe that basic mathematical operations are executed the fastest in C++, followed by Visual Basic. Mathematical operations in Python are executed between 5 and 70 times slower than in C++. The mathematical operations of addition, logarithmic calculations, and sine computations in Visual Basic are slightly slower than in C++, while the division operation is 4.6 times slower in Visual Basic compared to C++.

From this, we can conclude that for programs that perform a large number of mathematical computations, C++ is the optimal language to use due to its superior performance.

Table 4. Addition of two numbers within a double For loop

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Cycles	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000	10 000
Execution time (seconds)	0.219	0.1825	12.982	1.189
Standard deviation (seconds)	0	0.0072	0.139	0.0053

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 5. Division of two numbers in a double For loop

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Cycles	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000	10 000
Execution time (seconds)	1.656	0.359	12.376	1.215
Standard deviation (seconds)	0	0	0.1396	0.005331

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 6. Calculating the logarithm base 10 in a double For loop

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Cycles	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000	10 000
Execution time (seconds)	3.311	2.568	20.835	1.23
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.0137	0.0083	0.298	0.0028

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 7. Calculating the sine of an angle in a double For loop

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Cycles	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000	10 000
Execution time (seconds)	4.626	3.995	22.027	1.22
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.005	0.0077	0.14	0.0036

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

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In Table 8, the comparative results of the time measurement for writing are shown, and in Table 9, the results for reading an array of one million numbers into a text file with a .TXT extension. Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that the program in Visual Basic and C++ executes the fastest, while the Python program is approximately 4000 times slower at writing numbers to a text file. However, Python is faster at reading than writing data to a text file.

Table 8. Writing an array of numbers to a Notepad text file

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers - writing	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000
Execution time (seconds)	0.000162	0.000176	0.7274	93.52
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.0000079	0.0000075	0.0103	0.292

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 9. Reading an array of numbers from a Notepad text file

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers - reading	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000	100 000 000
Execution time (seconds)	0.000206	0.000197	0.1401	137.7
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.0000067	0.000008	0.0041	3.02

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

In Table 10, the comparative results of the time measurement for writing are shown, and in Table 11, the results for reading an array of 5000 numbers into a Microsoft Excel file with the .XLS extension. Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that the Python program executes the fastest. Python reads data faster than it writes to an Excel file. Here, it is worth noting the speed of writing and reading data into an Excel file using the VEEPro programming language, as it is only slightly slower compared to the other programming languages. This differs from the results shown in the previous tables when using a FOR loop, which significantly slows down the VEEPro program. This can be explained by the fact that the VEEPro programming language is primarily intended for communication with measuring instruments and for retrieving measured values into an Excel file.

Table 10. Writing an array of numbers to Microsoft Excel

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers - writing	5 000	5 000	5 000	5 000
Execution time (seconds)	9.688	6.837	5.996	19.99
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.861	0.585	0	0.218

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 11. Reading an array of numbers from a Notepad text file

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers - reading	5 000	5 000	5 000	5 000
Execution time (seconds)	8.879	12.431	3.998	10.835
Standard deviation (seconds)	1.879	0.133	0.0005	0.093

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

In Table 12, the comparative results of the time measurement for sorting an array of 25 000 000 numbers using the built-in SORT function are shown. What completely surprised us is that sorting the numbers was by far the fastest in the VEEPro programming language, where the best optimization of the SORT function was achieved for sorting the numbers. This is exactly what is needed when processing large amounts of measurement results.

In Table 13, the comparative results of the time measurement for sorting an array of 10 000 numbers using a double FOR loop are shown. Since this sorting is done with a FOR loop, the VEEPro programming language is again significantly slower, and for it, only the sorting time for an array of 100 numbers is shown. Once again, the C++ programming language proved to be the fastest.

Table 12. Sorting an array of numbers using the SORT function

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers	25 000 000	25 000 000	25 000 000	25 000 000
Execution time (seconds)	8.8695	2.137	4.146	0.0001964
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.0767	0.00655	0.0567	0.0000096

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 13. Sorting an array of numbers using a double FOR loop

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers	10 000	10 000	10 000	100
Execution time (seconds)	0.5675	0.1875	30.323	11.79
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.00725	0.00053	0.163	0.035
Relative deviation (%)	1.28	0.28	0.54	0.3

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

Table 14. Sorting an array of numbers using a double WHILE loop by finding the maximum element of the array

Programming language	Visual Basic	C++	Python	VEEPro
Array of numbers	10 000	10 000	10 000	100
Execution time (seconds)	0.169	0.1014	17.391	0.425
Standard deviation (seconds)	0.0067	0.00824	0.221	0.017

Note: This table was prepared by the authors

5. Conclusions

Modern measurements are completely unimaginable without the use of computers. Computers enable simultaneous control of multiple measuring instruments or measurement acquisition systems that collect measurement signals from a large number of sensors. Communication between the computer and measuring instruments can be achieved using various programming languages. This paper presents a comparison of the syntax and execution speed of four programming languages that can be used for communication with measuring instruments. Each programming language has its advantages, which is why they are used by developers worldwide. Visual Basic probably has the simplest syntax when

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writing branching and looping structures. This programming language performs basic mathematical operations very quickly and, in terms of execution speed, is only slightly slower than C++. The C++ programming language is typically the first one taught in schools. Our research showed that basic mathematical operations, as well as data reading and writing to text files, are performed fastest in C++. Python proved to be a programming language with simple the shortest code for basic commands. Python especially stood out as the fastest when writing and reading data to Excel documents, and most measurement data is suitable for processing and analysis when stored in Excel documents. Programming in the VEEPro language is completely different from writing code in the other three programming languages. Programming in VEEPro is done using ready-made objects that are placed on a workspace and then connected with lines by dragging the mouse from the output of one object to the input of another. Programmers have access to a large number of ready-made objects, some of which are particularly significant, such as objects simulating analog and digital instruments, oscilloscopes, various generators, and objects used for communication with measuring instruments. This programming language proved to be the slowest when using loop structures with FOR loops. However, to our great surprise, VEEPro proved to be by far the fastest when sorting large arrays using the built-in SORT function. This justifies its primary purpose of connecting computers and measuring instruments and retrieving numerous measured values.

Finally, we suggest that those who want to engage in remote control of measuring instruments choose the programming language that best suits their needs.

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POREĐENJE ČETIRI PROGRAMSKA JEZIKA ZA KOMUNIKACIJU SA MERNIM INSTRUMENTIMA

***Apstrakt:** Danas se računari primenjuju u merenjima u svim privrednim i industrijskim sektorima. Primena računara u metrologiji dovela je do značajnih promena u tehnikama merenja, posebno u pogledu električnih veličina. Za komunikaciju i upravljanje mernim instrumentima koriste se različiti programski jezici, od kojih svaki ima svoje prednosti i nedostatke. U ovom radu data je komparativna analiza svojstava i karakteristika nekoliko popularnih programskih jezika: Visual Basic-a, C++-a i Python-a, kao i VEEPro-a, jezika koji je posebno dizajniran za komunikaciju sa programiranim mernim instrumentima. Sličnosti i razlike između ova četiri programska jezika, pre svega su namenjene nastavnicima koji predaju Programiranje i Električna merenja u školama i na univerzitetima. Za potrebe ove studije, razvijeni su programi radi poređenja brzine izvršavanja ovih jezika na velikom broju ciklusa. Svi dobijeni rezultati u ovom radu, prikazani su tabelarno.*

***Ključne reči:** programski jezik, poređenje, brzina izvršavanja.*